

A STUDY ON PUBLIC AWARENESS AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS GOODS AND SERVICES TAX IN TIRUNELVELI CITY

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Abstract

This paper is an analysis of public awareness and satisfaction towards GST. In India, there are different indirect taxes applied on goods and services by both central and state government. GST is replacing multiple taxes levied by central and state Government. India is a democratic country, so here after long discussion only the GST will be implemented as CGST and SGST respectively, but still many of the people not aware Goods and Services Tax. This paper will help to analyses that, what will be the objective, impact of Goods and Services Tax, benefits and demerits of Goods and Services Tax.

Keywords: Introduction, Benefits, Methodology, Data analysis

Introduction

The word tax is derived from the Latin word 'taxare' its meaning to estimate. In India taxes are generally classified into two types, namely direct taxes and indirect taxes. Direct taxes are taxes on income of individual corporate, stamp duty and real estate. In indirect taxes are taxes on goods and services of sales including customs duties and excise duties. Generally, taxes are not directly paid to government but collected through intermediaries such as retail stores. In India each and every state follow different tax structure the tax rate also not uniform. This main reason only GST bill was introduced here the different taxes paid by us on different rates would be control under one head. The GST is expected to change the current Indirect Tax. Its help to develop our nation the slogan of GST in our country is "One tax one nation "

Benefits of GST

- It helps to eliminate the cascading impact of taxes on production and distribution of goods and services in our country.
- GST will help to improve the competitiveness of original goods and services.
- Its help to merging several Central and State taxes into a single tax structure.
- All the tax payment procedures are simplified such as registrations, returns, payments, etc. its help to traders and also public.
- GST its lead to an improved competitiveness for the trade and industry in our country
- GST would help to reduce the cost of locally manufactured goods and services

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Statement of the Problem

In India most of the state government is not accepted the GST bill. After long discussion only, the bill was passed. Still some tax rates are modified. After the introduction of GST bill still there is a lack of awareness among the general public as well as traders. Therefore, it is the need of this paper to have a study and identify the public awareness and satisfaction towards GST Bill.

Objectives of the study

- To study the public awareness and towards GST in Tirunelveli City
- To study the satisfaction level of respondents towards GST
- To Suggest suitable measurement about GST

Research Methodology

Research design	The research design adopted in the study was descriptive design
Area of study	The area of the study is in Tirunelveli City
Period of study	Study was conducted for the period one month
Source of Data	The study is based on primary and secondary data collection
Sampling Design	The sampling design is convenient sampling a sample 44 respondents
Tools for analysis	The collected data was analyse with the help of percentage table and five-point Likert's scale

Limitation of the study

The study is micro level and its covers only Tirunelveli City. The number of respondents of this study was 44.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Profile of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage	
1.	Gender	Male	28	63.64
		Female	16	36.36
		Total	44	100
2.	Age Group	20 - 30	08	18.18
		30 - 40	14	31.82
		40 -50	12	27.27
		Above 50	10	22.73
		Total	44	100
3.	Educational Qualification	School level	09	20.45
		Degree/ diploma	14	31.82
		Post-Graduation	11	25
		Professionals	10	22.73

Sl. No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage	
4.	Occupation	Total	44	100
		Government Employee	06	13.64
		Private Employee	16	36.36
		Professionals	10	22.73
		Business	12	27.27
		Total	44	100
5.	Monthly Income	Below 10000	05	11.36
		10000 - 20000	13	29.55
		20000 - 30000	14	31.82
		30000 - 40000	07	15.91
		Above 40,000	05	11.36
		Total	44	100

Table 1 reveals the demographic profile of the respondents here majority of the respondents are male (63.64 %). It is clear the out of 44 respondents 14 (31.82 %) respondents age group is 30 - 40. It further shows majority 14 (31.82 %) respondents have degree / diploma as educational qualification. Out of 44 respondents 16 (36.36 %) respondents' occupation was private employee. The level of monthly income differs from one to another, most of the 14 (31.82 %) belonged to this category ₹ 20000 - 30,000

Table 2: Level of awareness towards GST

Level of awareness	Very high	High	Medium	Low	Very Low	Total
Awareness towards GST	16 (36.36%)	11 (25 %)	07 (15.91 %)	06 (13.64 %)	04 (9.09 %)	44 (100 %)
Awareness on interstate transaction	09 (20.45%)	07 (15.91%)	05 (11.36%)	09 (20.45 %)	14 (31.82%)	44 (100%)
GST is easier than VAT	10 (22.73%)	11 (25 %)	08 (18.18%)	09 (20.45%)	06 (13.64%)	44 (100%)
Sales tax liability reduced	07 (15.91%)	09 (20.45%)	08 (18.18%)	10 (22.73%)	10 (22.73%)	44 (100%)
Aware the principle one nation one tax	14 (31.82%)	12 (27.27%)	08 (18.18%)	06 (13.64%)	04 (9.09%)	44 (100%)

Table 2 shows how aware the respondents towards the service of GST Out of the total respondents, 36.36 % are very high awareness about GST 14 (31.82 %) of the respondents saying they are getting very low-level awareness about interstate transaction. 25 % of the respondent's opinions

are GST is easier than VAT. 10 (22.73 %) respondents are very low-level awareness about sales tax liability. 31.82 % of the respondents getting very high awareness about the principle of one nation one tax

Table 3: Level of satisfaction towards GST

No	Particulars	Respondent's Response					Likert's Scale		
		SDA	DA	No idea	A	SA	Weighted score	Total Score	Percentile points
1.	Process of GST is simple	09	05	04	12	14	149	220	67.73
2.	Prices of goods are reduced	16	09	09	06	04	105	220	47.73
3.	GST removed the regional imbalances of state government	12	08	11	06	07	120	220	54.54
4.	GST reduced tax burden	08	12	10	09	05	123	220	55.90
5.	GST help to develop our nation	09	11	05	10	09	131	220	59.54

As per the above calculation a total 67.73 percentile shows better overall process of GST is simple. GST help to develop our nation also fine with 59.54 percentile points.

Conclusion

GST will face many challenges after long discussion only its implemented. It is basically structured and also is to simplify current Indirect tax system. GST reduced the multiple tax burden and help to reduce the regional imbalances of the state government. But most of the general public is almost unaware of the concept of GST. So, the creation of awareness is essential towards GST after only we conclude the process of GST is effective or ineffective.

References:

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